

Building Information Modeling (BIM) for Participatory Monitoring of Building Energy and Environmental Performance: The BIM4Citizens Project

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Abstract:

The BIM4Citizens Project addresses a critical disconnect identified in smart building research: the parallel advancement of technical systems (BIM, IoT, Digital Twins) and participatory methods, which often proceed without meaningful intersection. The BIM4Citizens initiative responds by proposing and testing an integrated socio-technical framework through a concrete pilot: the Verlaine Building case study at the University of Mons (UMONS). The project develops a four-phase methodological protocol for transforming heterogeneous building data into a coherent participatory digital ecosystem:

Phase 1: Data Consolidation. Through audit and inventory of existing data sources (geometric surveys, technical documentation, energy records), a centralized relational database is created. Existing BIM models are aligned using IFC export and Information Delivery Specification (IDS) to ensure consistent correspondence between geometric entities and database attributes.

Phase 2: Enrichment for Energy and Environmental Analysis. Building on the consolidated database, parametric scenario modeling evaluates envelope improvement strategies. For each wall type, current thermal performance is calculated alongside target performance (according to Belgian PEB standards), enabling comparative analysis of insulation materials based on thermal conductivity, cost, and thickness. Simultaneously, the data model is extended to accommodate real-time IoT data streams (temperature, CO₂, occupancy) via LoRaWAN sensors.

Phase 3: Participatory Dimension Integration. User feedback mechanisms are designed and deployed through simple interfaces (web/mobile forms) allowing occupants to report discomfort or evaluate thermal conditions periodically. These participatory data points are stored in the central database, linked to specific spaces via unique room identifiers, ensuring alignment with both the BIM model and sensor data.

Phase 4: Validation and Protocol Formalization. All data sources are cross-analyzed within a centralized visualization environment (Power BI, with potential integration into Autodesk Tandem for immersive digital twin experiences). Heatmaps of user complaints can be superimposed with measured temperatures and theoretical thermal losses, enabling evidence-based decision-making. The methodology is then formalized into a replicable "Verlaine Protocol," providing a generic framework for participatory digital twin development applicable at building, neighborhood, or urban corridor scale.

The presentation will detail this integrated architecture, the technical choices (IFC, IDS, IoT connectivity, visualization platforms), and initial findings on its effectiveness in fostering behavioral changes, improving thermal comfort, and enhancing energy efficiency. It demonstrates how closing the loop between digital twins and citizen science contributes to more inclusive and effective urban governance and Smart Cities objectives.

Keywords : BIM (Building Information Modeling), IoT (Internet of Things), Digital Twin, Participatory Monitoring.